

Breeding male sterile rice lines with droopy leaves

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RGS20 is an ideal donor in developing male sterile lines with droopy leaves. It was crossed with leading maintainers having erect leaves. Results confirmed

that a single recessive gene controls the droopy leaf trait.

In F_2 , B_1F_2 and B_2F_2 , the droopy-leaf plants with the desired characters were selected and backcrossed to erect-leaf B lines to identify droopy-leaf B lines. The droopy leaf trait was then incorporated into a wild abortive (WA) background by backcrossing to the droopy B. Some promising droopy leaf male sterile lines

with WA cytoplasm and improved agronomic traits were released in 1990.

Panicles of the droopy leaf A line are all located in the upper leaves, which favors the receipt of foreign pollen. Thus, more hybrid rice seed can be produced with less effort by using the droopy-leaf male sterile lines because producers do not have to cut flag leaves and spray gibberellin. ■

Suspension initiation in indica rice requires proline

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Suspension cultures are frequently used as starting material for protoplast isolation. We manipulated the suspension initiation medium to produce a fast-growing embryogenic line needed for successful protoplast culture.

Dehulled IR72 seeds were sterilized in 70% vol/vol ethanol for 1 min and 2.62% vol/vol sodium hypochlorite. They were inoculated in a plastic petri dish (100 × 15 mm) containing 20 ml modified MS medium for callus induction. The cultures were incubated in the dark at 25 ± 1 °C for 3 wk. Calli were subcultured for 2 wk before suspension initiation.

We selected the friable, smooth, light yellow calli (the group of densely cytoplasmic cells as observed in an inverted microscope) to initiate suspension. About 2 g calli were placed in a 125-ml Erlenmeyer flask containing 30 ml liquid medium. We used two sets of basal medium, N6 and R2. Each set

Effect of proline on the initiation of suspension in indica rice. With proline: a) Prolific growth of secondary calli. b) Separation of microcalli from MC.

Without proline: c) Poor initiation of secondary calli. d) Unsustained growth of secondary calli. e) Necrotic MC in N_6P_0 , R_2P_0 ; light yellow, smooth, friable microcalli in N_6P_{10} , R_2P_{10} 8 wk after initiation; finer microcalli in about 20-wk-old suspension in N_6P_5 .

had three proline levels: 0, 5, and 10 mM as P₀, P₅, and P₁₀, respectively.

Cultures were placed on a gyrotary shaker (120 rpm) in the dark at 25 ± 1 °C. About 3/4 of the liquid medium was replaced 2x/wk for the first 3-4 wk and weekly thereafter. The smaller calli with light yellow smooth surfaces were selected and transferred to another flask containing fresh medium. The cultures were maintained in the same medium until they were ready for protoplast isolation. See table for media additives.

The addition of proline (5 or 10 mM) in both basal media initiated the growth of secondary calli (indicated by arrows in the figure) on the periphery of the mother callus (MC) as observed in an inverted microscope 4 wk after initiation (fig. a). The secondary calli proliferated well and formed microcalli, which started to separate from the MC after 2 more weeks (fig. b). Such changes were not observed in the absence of proline in basal media

Media additives.

Additive	Concentration ^a (mg/liter)		
	MS	N ₆	R ₂
Nicotinic acid	0.5	0.5	0
Pyridoxine · HCl	0.5	0.5	0
Thiamine · HCl	0.1	1.0	1.0
Myo-inositol	100	0	0
2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid	2.0	1.0	1.0
Sucrose	30000	0	0
Maltose	0	30000	30000
Agarose (Sigma type I)	5500	0	0
Glycine	2.0	2.0	0
Casein hydrolysate	1000	0	0
Proline P ₀	-	0	0
P ₅	-	575.5	575.5
P ₁₀	-	1151.0	1151.0

^aAt pH 5.8.

(fig. c and d). Furthermore, 8 wk after initiation, the MC in the medium without proline started to become brown and hard, stopped growing, and died (fig. e, N₆P₀ and R₂P₀). The microcalli arising

from the MC in medium with proline were still light yellow, smooth, and friable, with about 3-4 mm diameter, and became finer as the culture aged (fig. e, N₆P₁₀, R₆P₁₀, and N₆P₅). ■

Yield potential

Ratoon crop performance in some rice hybrids

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We studied the possibility of using ratoon crops in some F₁ hybrids at the Sukamandi field station during the 1988-

89 wet season. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications in a 3- × 5-m² plot. Hybrids V20 A/IR64, V20 A/IR46 R, V20 A/Krueng-Aceh, V20 A/M66b, V20 A/IR28178, and V20 A/IR25912 and check Dodokan were ratooned by cutting mature stalks at 20 cm above the ground. We topdressed 40 kg N/ha immediately after cutting. The plots were irrigated as needed.

Ratoon hills/m² ranged from 20 for

V20 A/Krueng-Aceh to 25 for V20 A/IR25912. Yields ranged from 0.76 t/ha for V20 A/Krueng-Aceh to 1.27 t/ha for V20 A/IR28178, about 14-22% of the main crop yield (Table 1).

Number of filled spikelets/panicle of the ratoon crop varied from 69.3 for V20 A/Krueng-Aceh to 97.6 for V20 A/IR25912, about 62-92% that of the main crop. The ratoon of hybrid V20 A/IR46 showed the maximum number of panicles/hill at 11.95. The 1,000-grain

Table 1. Maturity, hill number, yield, filled grains/panicle, and stem rot of ratoon and main crops of some rice hybrids. Sukamandi, Indonesia, 1988-89 wet season.^a

Hybrid, check	Maturity (d)		Hills/m ² (no.)		Yield (t/ha)		Filled grains/panicle (no.)		Stem rot ^b	
	Main	Ratoon	Main	Ratoon	Main	Ratoon	Main	Ratoon	Main	Ratoon
V20 A/IR25912	122	62 (51)	25	25 (100)	4.1	1.3 (31)	105.38	97.62 (92) ^a	3	5
V20 A/IR46	120	62 (52)	25	25 (100)	5.1	0.9 (17)	107.20	79.87 (74)	3	5
V20 A/IR64	114	60 (53)	25	25 (100)	4.1	1.1 (27)	104.66	92.35 (88)	3	5
V20 A/Kr. Aceh	114	60 (53)	25	20 (80)	5.6	0.8 (14)	111.20	69.30 (62)	3	7
V20 A/IR28178	113	57 (50)	25	25 (100)	5.9	1.3 (22)	115.85	90.21 (77)	3	5
V20 A/M66b	109	60 (55)	25	25 (100)	5.9	0.8 (14)	115.21	76.20 (66)	3	7
Dodokan	101	53 (52)	25	21 (84)	5.1	0.9 (17)	102.91	80.50 (78)	1	1
LSD (0.05)	3	4			0.4	0.1	15.19	35.58		
CV (%)	1.1	2.7			3.4	2.6	5.7	17.4		

^aFigures in parentheses are % of main crop. ^bBased on *Standard evaluation system for rice*.